

Saponins and Sapogenins: Part XXXII. Studies on *Trigonella foenum-graecum* Linn. Seeds.

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The seeds of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* Linn. (Fenugreek) on extraction with ethanol yield a mixture of four flavonoid components (two glycosides and two aglycones) and two steroidal saponins. The flavonoid part consists of only two flavonoid aglycones from which quercetin has been isolated in pure form and identified by mixed melting point and superimposable IR spectra. The second flavonoid aglycone has been identified as luteolin by paper chromatography. The saponin part on hydrolysis yields two steroidal sapogenins, identified as diosgenin and gitogenin in 9 : 1 ratio.

Trigonella foenum-graecum Linn., a member of the family Leguminosae, sub-family, Papilionaceae, is commonly known as Fenugreek and Maithi in Hindi. Its leaves are used as vegetable (*sag*) and their poultice is useful in external and internal swellings and burns due to their cooling properties. The seeds of the plant are used as condiment, in colic flatulence, dysentery, diarrhoea, dyspepsia with loss of appetite, chronic cough, dropsy, enlargement of liver and spleen, rickets, gout, and diabetes.¹

Various members of the Leguminosae family have been studied for the saponin contents in these laboratories.² It was noted that all the sapogenins isolated from the members of this family belonged to the group of triterpenic sapogenins, but a review to the literature showed that the seeds of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* contain a steroidal saponin. Marker *et al.*³ in U.S.A., have reported the presence of three steroidal sapogenins identified as diosgenin, gitogenin and tigogenin, the latter being in traces. Recently Mme. Heitz⁴ has isolated four saponins from the seeds in France yielding only two sapogenins, diosgenin and gitogenin. Further the leaves of this plant have also been reported to contain a flavonoid, Quercetin⁵, Carotenoids⁶, a coumarin⁷ besides a number of other substances. However no work has at all been done on the flavonoid contents of these seeds. As it is known⁸ that sapogenins vary not only in the percentage contents but also in their nature with the place of origin of the seeds, so the study of the seeds in India was taken up.

Well defatted powdered seeds (Maithi) obtained from the local market were exhausted with ethanol. The recovery of ethanol gave a dark-brown gummy mass. It was refluxed

1. Nediarni, "Indian Materia Medica", Popular Book Depot, Bombay, 1954, p. 1240.
2. Varshney, "Leguminosae Saponins" paper presented at the symposium on "Glycosides and Saponins", Calcutta, 1964: CSIR., New Delhi (in the press) and references contained therein.
3. Marker *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2242.
4. Heitz, *Compt. rend.*, 1959, 248, 268.
5. Ganju and Puri, *J. Ind. Med. Res.*, 1959, 4, 563.
6. Sadana and Ahmad, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1949, 8B, 52.
7. Reppel and Wagenbreth, "Flora", 1958, pp. 212-27.

successively with petroleum ether, ether, acetone, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform. The recovery of ether left a dark-red gummy mass, which by paper chromatography showed the presence of two flavonoids. The concentration of acetone extract also gave a dark-red gummy product, which also gave two spots of flavonoids (different from the ones obtained in the ether extract) by paper chromatography.

The separation and purification of the flavonoids on Whatman Filter Paper No. 3 gave four products, two of which were found to be free aglycones and the remaining two (from acetone) as glycosides. The glycosides on hydrolysis with 8% sulphuric acid furnished two aglycones, which were purified by chromatography on Magnesol. These were found to be identical with the free aglycones reported earlier in ether extract. One of the aglycones on crystallisation with methanol had m.p. 310-12° (cf. quercetin m.p. 316-17°). Its identity was further confirmed by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, paper chromatography, and superimposable IR spectra.

The second aglycone could not, however, be crystallised due to paucity of the material and seemed to be identical with luteolin by paper chromatography in different solvents alongside with authentic sample of luteolin.

The ethanolic extract after extraction with various solvents responded to all tests for steroidal saponins. The saponin on hydrolysis with 8-10% H_2SO_4 provided a brown solid genin, which was purified by sodium salt formation and extraction with ether. The recovery of ether provided a pale-yellow product. This on paper chromatography showed the presence of two genins, which were purified by chromatography on alumina. The two products, thus obtained, on crystallisation had m.p. 203-05° and 268-69°. These were identified as diosgenin and gitogenin respectively (diosgenin m.p. 204-07° and gitogenin m.p. 270-72°) the genin, m.p. 203-05°, showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with an authentic sample of diosgenin and had superimposable IR spectra. The acetate of the genin m.p. 203-05° melted at 188-90° (Diosgenin acetate m.p. 190°).

EXPERIMENTAL*

Well-powdered seeds (1 kg.) purchased from the local market were defatted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum (40-60°). The recovery of the solvent left a dark-red oil (210 gms.).

The well-defatted dry seed-powder was exhausted with 95% ethanol. The recovery of ethanol left a dark-brown gummy mass which was refluxed well successively (twice each) with light petroleum ether, acetone, CCl_4 , and $CHCl_3$, leaving saponin as a yellowish brown mass.

Purification of Ether-soluble Flavonoids.—The extract, obtained by the extraction of the ethanolic extract with ether, on recovery furnished a brownish yellow product which responded to tests for free flavonoids. On chromatography on filter paper it showed presence of two free aglycones (flavonoids) and therefore these were quantitatively separated by chromatography applying as streaks on pre-washed Whatman filter paper No. 3, using butanol:acetic acid:water (4:1:5)—saturated solution as the solvent. The papers

*All the melting points recorded in this paper have been taken on a Kofler hot microscopical stage and are corrected.

were run for 12 hrs. and the line spots were revealed by ammonia vapours. The two yellow line spots were cut from filter papers and separately exhausted with ethanol in a Soxhlet apparatus. The recovery of ethanol in one case provided a solid product, but in the other, a gummy matter.

Purification of Acetone-soluble Flavonoids.—Acetone extract on chromatography also showed the presence of two flavonoid glycosides and were purified by chromatography on alumina, but no separation could be effected.

Hydrolysis of Acetone-soluble Flavonoids.—The purified flavonoids of acetone extract were hydrolysed with 8% H_2SO_4 in the usual manner. The resulting product was extracted with ether, washed with water to remove acid and dried. The recovery of ether afforded a gummy solid.

Purification of Flavonoid Aglycones.—The ether-soluble flavonoids as well as aglycones, obtained by hydrolysis of acetone extract, was purified by chromatography on magnesol using dry acetone as eluent. In both the cases two fractions were obtained. One fraction from each could be crystallised (I) while the other present in smaller quantities was gummy (II).

Paper Chromatography of the Aglycones.—The two aglycone fractions, thus obtained from each part, were chromatographed on Whatman filter paper No. 1, using butanol: acetic acid-water (4:1:5) as solvent alongside with authentic samples of various known flavonoids. The papers were run for 12 hrs. and were revealed by (i) ammonia vapour, (ii) $EtOH-FeCl_3$ solution. In both the cases two spots were obtained which were identical with each other. In various solvents the spots obtained corresponded well with the spots of quercetin and luteolin (Table I).

TABLE I

Rf values of

Solvents	Solid flavonoid (I)	Gummy flavonoid (II)	Quercetin, authentic	Luteolin, authentic
BuOH: AcOH: H_2O (4:1:5)	0.78	0.84	0.785	0.807
HAc: Water (8:4)	0.40	0.42	0.40	0.43
Phenol: water (73:27 w/v)	0.40	0.705	0.42	0.72

Crystallisation of the Flavonoid Aglycones.—One of the flavonoid aglycones (with lower *Rf* value) on crystallisation in methanol had m.p. $310-12^\circ$ (Quercetin $310-17^\circ$) and did not depress the m.p. when mixed with an authentic sample of quercetin and had superimposable IR spectra. The other fraction showing higher *Rf* values could not be crystallised.

Purification of Saponin.—The purified yellow mass after extraction with various solvents was dissolved in a small quantity of ethanol and precipitated twice in large volumes of ether, the process of dissolution and precipitation was repeated in acetone when a light-yellow powder (12.5 g.) was obtained, which turned to a thick syrup on exposure to air. This responded to all the tests for saponin.

Chromatography of Saponins.—The saponin, thus obtained, was chromatographed on Whatman filter paper No.1, using upper layer of butanol: acetic acid: water (4:1:5) mixture (ascending). The spots were revealed by spraying the solution of *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde in ethanol: phosphoric acid: perchloric acid (0.25 g.) (25 ml: 10 ml: 4 ml). This showed the presence of two spots with different *R_f* values.

Hydrolysis of Saponin.—The saponin (12.5 g.) was dissolved in water (5 litres) and hydrolysed with 8-10% H₂SO₄ by first heating for an hour on a boiling water bath and then refluxing for ¼ hr. A light-brown solid (genins) separating was filtered, washed free of acid with water and dried (4.0 g.)

Purification of Sapogenins.—The genins (4.0 g.) dissolved in methanol (200 ml) were refluxed with MeOH-NaOH (20 g. NaOH in 250 ml MeOH) for ¼ hr. The half of the solvent was distilled and the resulting product was poured on water (15,00 ml) and extracted with ether four times. The ether extracts were washed free of alkali. The recovery of ether yielded a pale-yellow solid (1.1 g.).

Paper Chromatography of the Genins.—The genin mixture was chromatographed on Whatman filter paper No. 1 using butanol: acetic acid: water (4:1:5) as the solvent. The spots were revealed by *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde solution in acid medium whereby two spots were obtained.

Separation of Sapogenins.—The sapogenin mixture (1.1 gm.) was chromatographed on Alumina (50 gms.) and eluted with 25 cc fractions of the following solvents (Table II).

Fraction	Solvent	Substance obtained	Weight
I-II	Benzene: chloroform (98:2)	Blank	—
III-XIII	do	m.p. 203-05°	0.9 gm.
XIV	Benzene chloroform (80:20)	m.p. 268-69°	0.1 gm.
XV	do	Blank	—
XVI-XVIII	do	Blank	—
XIX-XX	Chloroform	oily drops	—

The fractions III to XIII on crystallisation in methanol gave colourless needles m.p. 203-05 (0.90 gms) (cf. diosgenin 204-07, mixed m.p. with authentic sample 203-05) and had superimposable IR spectra with diosgenin. The fraction XV on crystallisation from methanol had m.p. 268-69° (0.10 gms.) (cf. gitogenin 270-72°).

Acetylation of the Genin.—The genin, m.p. 203-05° was acetylated with pyridine and acetic anhydride in cold in the usual manner. On crystallisation with methanol the acetate melted at 189-90° (diosgenin acetate m.p. 190°) mixed m.p. with authentic sample showed no depression.

Deacetylation of the Genin Acetate.—The acetate, m.p. 189-90° on deacetylation with MeOH-KOH gave back the genin, m.p. 203-05°, confirmed by mixed m.p. with the starting material samples.

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